
CBCS System In Higher Education: Impact & Challenges

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Abstract:

The aim of Education is the all-around development of the students. The development of their cognitive abilities is important simultaneously with affective and psychomotor development. All educational institutions are emphasizing all-around development. Five Year Plan of India proposed various measures for academic reforms in higher education. Indian higher education institutions need an infusion of new models to keep the curriculum responsive to the changing environment which includes technology adoption, changing industry requirements, changing aspiration of students, and changing expectations of society. CBCS aims to redefine the curriculum for keeping pace with the liberalization and globalization in education. Choice-Based Credit System (CBCS) has several unique features as advanced learning opportunities, ability to match students' scholastic and non-scholastic needs and aspirations, inter-institution transferability of students, partial completion of an academic program in the institution of enrolment, and partial completion in a specialized institution, improvement in academic quality and excellence, flexibility for the students to complete the program over an extended period of time, standardization and comparability of educational programs across the globe, etc. The CBCS may fit appropriately into the emerging socio-economic milieu and also respond effectively to the educational and occupational aspirations of future generations. CBCS provides a better facility to the learners like freedom, flexibility, advanced learning opportunities, fulfillment of student's academic needs and aspirations, intra and inter-institutional transferability, a quality education, etc. However, during the implementation of this system in higher education institutions, many challenges need to be addressed to put it on the right track. Therefore, the objective of the present paper is to examine the prospects and challenges of Choice Based Credit System.

Keywords: A Reform in Higher Education in India, Challenges & Suggestions

Introduction:

Introduction The aim of Education is the all-round development of the students. Development of their cognitive abilities is important simultaneously with affective and psychomotor development. All educational institutions are emphasizing the all-round development. Five Year plan of India proposed various measures for academic reforms in higher education. The National

Knowledge Commission in its report to the nation in 2008-2009 on higher education and Yashpal Committee Report in 2009 recommended overhauling of higher education through academic and administrative reforms. The purpose of such reform was to establish the higher education of India on international level equivalent to developed nations. University Grant Commission (11th plan, March 2009) and

Association of Indian Universities (AIU) stressed on the Choice Based Credit System. The present generation is in the state of dilemma. There's need to provide such an opportunities so that learner may have better choice. UGC has recommended for CBCS to all of the central universities in 2015-2016. The opportunities can't be utilized until the learners and the teachers are not well known. Therefore it is necessary to know each and every aspect of CBCS. CBCS provides a better facility to the learners like freedom, flexibility, advanced learning opportunities, fulfillment of student's academic needs and aspirations, intra and inter institutional transferability, a quality education etc. It is a cafeteria approached system, where standardizations of educational programs are maintained. It has some complex system, just as a tree of different branches and different fruits, according to the needs, the receiver can obtain that. But the significant role is that of administrator, so that everything should be clear and in the reach of every person (Chaubey 2015)

Challenges in CBCS:

Each element of the academic community is often resistant to change when a new system is implemented. It is difficult to accept grades as an alternative to marks and letters in place of actual complete marks since assignment of grades for particular ranks cannot be done only by referring to grades of grades and letter grades. Outside the major topic area, credit may dilute depth in the primary field of study. Students may find it difficult to choose subjects since they may not know how to foresee future demands. Because the overall number of students in a class varies by school, and

because students can choose any topic for a specific course at any college. In that circumstance, a professor's workload may fluctuate throughout numerous semi-annual intervals. To attract a significant number of students to a particular programme, the university must give excellent facilities, top teaching, and a huge number of optional candidates at reasonable fees. It is not cost-effective or time-effective for a student to enrol in multiple colleges for different courses at the same time. Students cannot stay in a single institution's hostel since they are enrolled in many institutions. Students are required to pay university fees for their studies at many schools, with the total amount of fees paid always exceeding the charge paid to a single institution.

Basic Features of CBCS:

1. Semesters: Every year is split into two semesters and therefore the assessment of students is conducted semester-wise. The learners have the opportunities to select courses from a pool of courses every semester. The results are declared at the end of every semester. Each semester has 15–18 weeks of academic training and assessment which is equal to 90 teaching days.

2. Credit System: The credit system is a redefining of the curriculum into smaller measurable entities or modules whereby these modules can be combined in different ways to qualify for a certificate, diploma, or degree. Each course is assigned a certain credit. The students can earn credits consistent with their pace by taking any amount of time.

3. Evaluation system: In many of the educational institutions formative as well as summative evaluation system is followed. In

Dr. HSGVV 40% wattage is given to formative while 60% to summative. This 40% is divided into two midterm exams of 20 marks. The end-term exam consists of 60 marks.

4. Course: Usually mentioned as 'papers' may be a component of a program. All courses need not carry the same weightage. The learning objectives and learning outcomes of each course should be defined clearly. A course may be designed to comprise lectures, tutorials, laboratory work, fieldwork, activities, project work, vocational training, viva-voce, seminars, term tests, assignments, presentations, self-learning activities, or a combination of some of these.

5. Choice of courses: There are provisions to select the courses consistent with learners' own interest, aptitude, ability, and objectives. There are three types of courses as directed by the UGC.

6. Core Course: There could also be a Core Course every semester. This is the course that is to be compulsorily studied by a student as a core requirement to accomplish the requirement of a program in a said discipline of study.

7. Foundation Course: The Foundation Courses may be of two kinds: Compulsory Foundation and Elective foundation. "Compulsory Foundation" courses are the courses based upon the content that leads to Knowledge enhancement. They are mandatory for all disciplines. Elective Foundation courses are value-based and are aimed at man-making education.

8. Audit Course: A student has an option of auditing some courses, grades obtained in such a course are not counted towards the calculation of grade point average. However,

a Pass grade is essential for earning credits for an audit course.

9. Project Work: Project work/ Dissertation work is a special course involving the application of knowledge in solving/analyzing/ exploring a real-life situation/difficult problem.

10. Elective Course: Elective course may be a course that may be chosen from a pool of papers. An elective course could also be supportive to the discipline of study, providing an expanded scope, enabling exposure to another discipline/domain, nurturing student's proficiency/skill. An elective could also be a "Generic Elective" that specializes in those courses which add generic proficiency to the students. An elective could also be "Discipline centric" or could also be chosen from an unrelated discipline. It can be called an "Open Elective."

11. Ability Enhancement Courses (AEC): The Ability Enhancement (AE) Courses could also be of two kinds: Ability Enhancement Compulsory Courses (AECC) and Skill Enhancement Courses (SEC). "AECC" courses are the courses that are based upon the content that results in Knowledge enhancement. Ability Enhancement Compulsory Courses are mandatory for all disciplines. Skill Enhancement Courses are value-based or skill-based and are aimed towards providing hands-on training, competencies, skills, etc.

12. Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA): It's a measure of the cumulative performance of a student over all the semesters. The CGPA is the ratio of total credit points scored by a student in various courses in all semesters and the sum of the total credits of all courses in all the

semesters. It is expressed up to two decimal places.

13. Semester Grade Point Average (SGPA): It's a measure of the performance of tasks accomplished in a semester. It is the ratio of total credit points scored by a student in various courses registered in a semester and the total course credits taken during that semester. It is also expressed up to two decimal places.

14. Provision of Credit Transfer: Credit Transfer means that credits earned at one institution for one or more courses under a given program are accepted under another program either by the same institution or another institution. This acceptance of earlier acquired credits may be done in one of two ways: (i) Direct Performance Transfer (ii) Course exemption.

15. Allotment of Grading: UGC has introduced a Ten-point grading system in CBCS to allot grading.

Suggestions for Implementation of CBCS in Higher Education in India:

1. Equalization in standard of education system should be maintained so that mobility of students could be checked.
2. All the P.G college of India should also be brought under the CBCS, as they also catering the responsibility of Higher Education on a large scale.
3. Selection of papers and choosing credits should be governed by the concerned department/ institution.
4. Provision of both Percentage and grading system should be maintained.

5. Professional training should be given to the teachers to handle it effectively.
6. Undoubtedly, CBCS is students' friendly but things are yet to be cacy of it. Class room teaching should be needed to justify the ef given importance.
7. To make it more effective, guidance and counselling services should be arranged for the teachers and students while choosing soft core papers.
8. Care should be taken about the gap between Central and state Universities in regard to quality of education as well as the availability of infrastructure at point.
9. Seminars, Conferences and debate should be organised to discuss its merits and demerits in detail.
10. Its adaptation should be optional or choice based rather than mandatory.

Conclusion:

A choice-based credit system is essential for higher education. Both the instructor and the pupils become more honest as a result of this approach. In the modern era, overcoming socio-economic issues and adopting new system innovation is seen as a crucial way for recovery, prosperity, and long-term growth sustainability (World Economic Forum, 2010). To summarise, education is not a goal, but rather an essential process in the development of a nation's youth, and later on a global scale. A well-designed assessment system is an effective instructional technology. CBCS has successfully lowered root learning as well as stored critical

thinking and analysis, all of which contribute to educational system creativity and innovation. Students view CBCS as a student centered student that allows student independence and transparent evaluation with a clear syllabus and appropriate college resources to improve all rounds. The important factors have been concluded. CBCS will therefore allow for a seamless transformation from a professor-centered to a student-centered system. The UGC has constantly launched initiatives towards cost effectiveness and quality in the “Indian Higher Education System”. The fundamental aims to widen educational excellence in overall system which includes teaching learning and evaluation process. However, many universities across the country have used a variety of test, evaluation, and grading methods to date. In view of this diversity, using a "choice-based credit system" to evaluate a single grading system as a student's overall performance appears to be a sensible method.

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